

Characterization of Yield Components, Physiological Traits and Oil Quality Parameters in Different Peanut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) Genotypes

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Abstract

This study aimed to characterize 13 different peanut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) genotypes in terms of yield components, physiological traits and oil quality parameters. The research was conducted in 2023 under Denizli-Çal conditions in a randomized block design with three replications. The genotypes examined were TR80-0042, Ayşehanım, Halisbey, TR80-0019, TR80-0020, TR80-0021, Masal, TR80-0071, TR80-0033, TR80-0034, TR80-0080, NC-7 and Rigel. Yield, hundred pod weight, hundred seed weight, shelling ratio, number of pods per plant, first and second quality pod ratios, oil content, oil yield and chlorophyll parameters at flowering and pod stages were evaluated. The results showed that there were statistically significant differences among genotypes in all parameters except chlorophyll b at flowering. Yield varied between 321.18-575.74 kg da⁻¹, with the highest yield (575.74 kg da⁻¹) in Masal variety. There was a strong positive correlation ($r=0.8933$) between oil yield and yield, while a negative correlation ($r=-0.2791$) was observed between yield and oil content. Principal component analysis showed that PC1 and PC2 explained 45.7% of the total variance. Hierarchical cluster analysis revealed that distinct groups were formed among genotypes. These results indicate that multidimensional evaluation should be made in genotype selection in peanut breeding programs and that different genotypes have advantages in different traits.

Research Article

Article History

Received :01.07.2025
Accepted :15.08.2025

Keywords

Peanut
yield
oil content
multivariate analysis

1. Introduction

Peanut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) is an annual plant cultivated as a summer crop from the legume family. It, which is in the oilseed category, is of great importance with its high oil content. It is an important food source because it contains fat, protein, carbohydrate and vitamins that are important in human and animal nutrition (Özel, 2023). Peanut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.), which has a wide cultivation area throughout the world, is a very important source of oil and protein. This plant, which has an important place in the food and agriculture sector, provides an important income to producers. This plant, which has a serious commercial potential in the national and international market, offers important contributions both as an oil source and as a snack (Ögetürk and Karaslan, 2025). Depending on the variety, peanut seeds have an oil content of 44-56%. The oil obtained from peanuts has superior properties in terms of flavor and other vegetable oils. The fact that it contains fatty acids, which are essential for high temperature resistance and healthy nutrition, increases the value of peanut oil. Peanut oil contains high levels of tocoferol. Tocopherol is an antioxidant substance that prevents oxidation and deterioration of the oil (Arioğlu, 2000). In addition, peanut seeds contain 24-30% protein. The fact that the amino acids in the structure of these proteins are easily digestible increases their nutritional value (Ahmed and Young, 1982). In 2023, peanut was cultivated on 30.92 million ha with a production of 54.27 million tonnes and the average pod yield was 1775.2 kg ha⁻¹ in the world. In Türkiye, thousands of tons of peanut were produced from 57.0 thousand ha of peanut cultivation. With a pod yield of 4280 kg ha⁻¹ in 2024, it had a yield value above the world average (Anonymous, 2025a,b). In Türkiye, 20% of the peanut is produced in Adana, 10% in Osmaniye, and 6% in Şırnak, while the rest is produced in other provinces. In addition, 95% of peanut marketing and processing activities in Turkey are carried out in Osmaniye province (Anonymous, 2025b). At the same time, peanut, like other legumes, binds the free nitrogen of the air to the soil and

leaves a soil rich in nitrogen and organic matter for the plant to be planted after it. Studies have shown that during a growing period, peanut plants accumulate 4.5-15.0 kg of nitrogen per decare from the free nitrogen of the air thanks to Rhizobium bacteria living in the roots (Woodroof, 1983). Peanut is a hoe plant. Since the soil is hoed during the growing period, weeds are removed and the soil is aerated. Therefore, it can be considered as a good crop rotation plant (Arioğlu, 2014). It is successfully cultivated as a main crop and as a second crop after wheat harvest. Peanut is one of the advantageous crops for farmers due to its high yield potential, the fact that it is not affected by whitefly and many other pests economically, ease of marketing and high income from unit area (Kurt et al., 2016). In peanut farming, in order to obtain high yield from unit area and to make profitable production, it is necessary to select varieties suitable for the region and growing conditions as well as timely and technically appropriate cultural practices. For this reason, adaptation studies are carried out in different locations in order to determine the varieties and lines suitable for regional conditions (İşler et al., 1997; Söğüt et al., 2002; Çalışkan and Arioğlu, 2004; Arslan et al., 2005; Kurt et al., 2009). The varieties used in peanut farming should be high-yielding and have good pod quality (thin shelled) and seed quality. Most of the peanuts produced in our country (95%) are consumed as nuts. Therefore, seed size (100 seed weight) and seed coat color vary according to consumer preference (Bakal et al., 2022). Ecological characteristics of the cultivated region and adaptation of the cultivated species to environmental conditions are the main factors affecting development physiology, product quality and yield in crop production. Although peanut has a wide adaptation ability, it can be grown as a first or second crop in many regions, and the determining factor appears to depend on the variety and adaptation to environmental factors as a result of correlation analyzes (Savemore et al., 2017). Peanut has a high genetic variation in terms of morphological-agronomic characters. In order to fully reveal this potential, studies to

determine the varieties that can adapt to the regional conditions in terms of yield and yield parameters and appropriate agronomic techniques are of considerable importance. The aim of this study was to determine the effects of the most suitable cultivar or cultivars on yield and yield components among 13 different peanut cultivars under Denizli conditions. It is expected that the results of the study will be an auxiliary source for the producers of the region in planning similar researches and will shed light on the scientific studies to be carried out in the region in the future.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Plant material and experimental area

The experiment was established in the main crop conditions of Çal district, Denizli province, during the 2023 peanut planting season. The 13 different peanut genotypes used in the research were obtained from the Osmaniye Oilseeds Research Institute Directorate. All genotypes (13) belong to the Virginia market type. When examined in terms of origin, the vast majority of genotypes (12) are of Turkish origin, whereas only one genotype (NC-7) originates from the United States of America. The genotypes used in the study are as follows: TR80-0042, Ayşehanım, Halisbey, TR80-0019, TR80-0020, TR80-0021, Masal, TR80-0071, TR80-0033, TR80-0034, TR80-0080, NC-7, and Rigel. A soil sample was taken from 0-30 cm depth before planting. Soil analysis was performed to

determine the physical and chemical properties of the sample. Some physical and chemical properties determined as a result of the analysis of the soil sample taken from 0-30 cm depth by Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam University Soil Department are given in Figure 1 (Anonymous, 2025c). The soil analysis results from the Denizli-Çal research area (0-30 cm depth) reveal moderately alkaline conditions with a pH of 8.3, exceeding the neutral range. The electrical conductivity (EC) measurement of $450 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ indicates non-saline soil conditions. The soil exhibits a notably high lime content (25.77%), which may influence nutrient dynamics and availability. Macronutrient analysis demonstrates adequate levels of potassium (365 mg kg^{-1}) and phosphorus (26.37 mg kg^{-1}). However, the organic matter content (1.17%) is considerably below the recommended threshold for agricultural soils (2-5%), suggesting potential limitations in soil structure, water retention capacity, and nutrient cycling efficiency. Regarding micronutrient status, copper (1.7 mg kg^{-1}) and manganese (11.4 mg kg^{-1}) concentrations appear sufficient, while iron (5.4 mg kg^{-1}) levels are marginally adequate but may be affected by the high soil pH and calcareous nature. The zinc concentration (0.4 mg kg^{-1}) is notably deficient. These soil characteristics indicate that the research area possesses moderate fertility with specific limitations related to high alkalinity, elevated lime content, low organic matter, and micronutrient imbalances, particularly zinc deficiency (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Soil analysis results (0-30 cm depth)

The experiment was conducted in 2023 at the Research and Application Center of the Faculty of Agriculture, Pamukkale University,

in Çal district, Denizli. Climate data for the main crop growing season for Denizli-Çal conditions are given in Figure 2.

Figure 2. 2023 years precipitation, average temperature and relative humidity data for the experimental area (April-October average during the main crop growing season)

The temperature, precipitation, and relative humidity data for the months during which the research was conducted, obtained from the Denizli Meteorological Station Directorate, are presented in Figure 2 for the year 2023. In Denizli-Çal district, during the April-October period of 2023, the monthly total precipitation amount was 295.5 mm, average temperature values ranged between 10.5 °C (April) and 27.1°C (August), and the average relative humidity values varied between 42.6% (July) and 75.4% (May). During the research period, the highest precipitation was recorded in May (125.4 mm), while the lowest precipitation was observed in August (5.2 mm). In the first half of the vegetation period (April-June), 82% of the total precipitation (243.2 mm) occurred, while a significant decrease in precipitation was observed in the second half (July-October). Temperature values showed a regular increase starting from April, reaching the maximum level in August, and subsequently decreased gradually. Relative humidity values, inversely proportional to the temperature increase, decreased significantly in the second half of the vegetation period (Figure 2) (Anonymous, 2024).

2.2. Method

The research was conducted at the Research

and Application Center of the Faculty of Agriculture, Pamukkale University, in Çal District, Denizli, located at coordinates 38°05'57" north latitude and 29°25'04" east longitude in the Aegean Region. The experiment was established using a randomized complete block design with three replications. The total experimental area was 764,40 m², with plot dimensions of 2.8 m × 5.0 m (14 m²), with 13 plots in each block and each plot consisting of 4 rows of plants. Before planting, the row spacing was 70 cm, and 132.0 seeds were planted per plot manually in furrows opened with a marker at a depth of 6-7 cm. The distance between blocks in the experiment was arranged as 3 m. Just before planting, 30 kg da⁻¹ of Diammonium phosphate (18% N, 46% P₂O₅) fertilizer was applied and mixed into the soil. After planting, 15 kg da⁻¹ of Urea (46% N) fertilizer was applied as top dressing. All necessary maintenance operations including weed control, disease and pest management, and irrigation were carried out throughout the growing season. Harvesting was done manually by pulling the plants in the plots and leaving them upside down to dry. Threshing was performed manually when the plant leaves turned brown and the above-ground parts dried. Physiological measurements were taken at two critical

growth stages: 50% flowering and pod formation. Total chlorophyll content, chlorophyll a, and chlorophyll b were measured using a Falker brand CFL260 model chlorophyll meter during both stages. The following yield and quality parameters were evaluated: yield (kg da^{-1}), one hundred pod weight (g), one hundred seed weight (g), shelling ratio (%), number of pods per plant, first quality pod rate (%), second quality pod rate (%), oil content (%), and oil yield (kg da^{-1}). Oil content was determined using standard laboratory procedures, and oil yield was calculated based on seed yield and oil content. The data obtained from the plant samples of the varieties from each plot were subjected to analysis of variance and mean comparisons were made to evaluate the performance of different genotypes under the experimental conditions.

2.3. Statistical analysis

The field experiment was established on May 11, 2023, following a Randomized Complete Block Design with three replications. Data obtained from both years were also evaluated to calculate basic statistical parameters such as mean, minimum and maximum values, standard deviation, coefficient variation, principal component analysis, cluster analysis, and biplot graphing using JMP (pro-17). For all measured parameters, including yield components, physiological traits, and oil quality parameters, descriptive statistics were calculated to determine means, standard deviations, and range values. To assess differences among the thirteen peanut genotypes, data were subjected to one-way analysis of variance (Anova). When significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were detected, means were separated using Tukey's Honest Significant Difference (HSD) test at 5% probability level using the agricolae package (Mendiburu, 2023). The homogeneity of variances was verified using Levene's test prior to ANOVA. To identify patterns of similarity among genotypes based on multiple traits simultaneously, hierarchical cluster analysis was performed using Euclidean distance as the dissimilarity measure and

Ward's minimum variance method for clustering. The resulting dendrogram was used to identify groups of genotypes with similar performance characteristics (Wickham, 2016).

3. Results and Discussion

When the descriptive statistics of the parameters examined in the study were evaluated, it was determined that the yield values varied between $321.18\text{-}575.74 \text{ kg da}^{-1}$, the average yield was $438.54 \text{ kg da}^{-1}$ and had a coefficient of variation of 16.18%. The descriptive statistics of the parameters examined in a study showed that pod yield values varied between $341.20\text{-}485.24 \text{ kg da}^{-1}$, the average yield was $407.56 \text{ kg da}^{-1}$ and had a coefficient of variation of 16.18%. These values are in parallel with our findings (Beycioğlu and Kılıç, 2025). 100-pod weight varied between $182.67\text{-}285.33 \text{ g}$, the average value was 242.03 g and 11.20% coefficient of variation was obtained. 100-seed weight ranged from a minimum of 119.74 g to a maximum of 179.01 g , with a mean value of 147.26 g and a low coefficient of variation of 10.88%. In peanut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.), 100 pod and 100 seed weight are of great importance in terms of yield components. Miao et al. (2023) reported that 100 pod weight and 100 seed weight are important components affecting peanut yield. The shelling ratio varied between 52.91-71.78%, with an average value of 61.04% and a coefficient of variation of 9.26%. The number of pods per plant varied between 23.93-36.20, with an average value of 30.48 and a coefficient of variation of 12.79%. According to Arıoğlu et al. (2018), the economic value of peanut is largely determined by its shelling ratio, which stands as one of the most crucial quality parameters. The first quality pod ratio varied between 65.68-82.91% with an average value of 74.55% and exhibited a stable characteristic with a low coefficient of variation of 6.89%. The percentage of second quality pods varied between 15.63-30.33%, with a mean value of 22.14% and a high coefficient of variation of 19.87%, making it the most variable trait (Table 1).

Table 1. Descriptive statistics values of the investigated agromorphological characteristics of peanut genotypes

Variable	Abbreviation	Unit	Min	Max	Mean	StDev	CV%
Yield	Yield	kg da ⁻¹	321.18	575.74	438.54	70.98	16.18
One hundred pod weight	OHuPoWe	g	182.67	285.33	242.03	27.12	11.20
One hundred seed weight	OHuSeWe	g	119.74	179.01	147.26	16.02	10.88
Shelling ratio	SeRa	%	52.91	71.78	61.04	5.65	9.26
Number of pods per plant	NuPoPePl	quantity	23.93	36.20	30.48	3.99	12.79
First quality pod rate	FiQuPoRa	%	65.68	82.91	74.55	5.14	6.89
Second quality pod rate	SeQuPoRa	%	15.63	30.33	22.14	4.40	19.87

Total chlorophyll content during the flowering period varied between 35.98-50.51 FCI, with an average value of 42.84 FCI and a coefficient of variation of 9.59%. Chlorophyll a content during the flowering period varied between 24.92-34.67 FCI with an average value of 29.51 FCI and exhibited a stable structure with a coefficient of variation of 9.11%. Chlorophyll b content in the flowering period varied between 10.22-15.55 FCI, with an average value of 12.60 FCI and a coefficient of variation of 14.13%. Total chlorophyll content in the pod stage varied between 37.20-55.67 FCI, with an average value of 43.02 FCI and a coefficient of variation of 11.78%.

Chlorophyll a content in the pod stage varied between 25.22-40.22 FCI, with an average value of 28.96 FCI and a coefficient of variation of 13.22%. Chlorophyll b content at pod stage varied between 8.89-15.89 FCI with an average value of 13.27 FCI and a coefficient of variation of 16.58%. Oil content varied between 44.59-51.25% and was found to be the most stable trait with an average value of 48.17% and the lowest coefficient of variation of 3.92%. Oil yield varied between 89.18-188.37 kg da⁻¹ with an average value of 128.85 kg da⁻¹ and exhibited high variability with a coefficient of variation of 19.32% (Table 2).

Table 2. Descriptive statistics values of the investigated physiological and characteristics of peanut genotypes

Variable	Abbreviation	Unit	Min	Max	Mean	StDev	CV%
Total chlorophyll amount during flowering period	TaChAmDuFlPe	FCI (Falker Chlorophyll Index)	35.98	50.51	42.84	4.11	9.59
Chlorophyll a during flowering	ChADuFl	FCI (Falker Chlorophyll Index)	24.92	34.67	29.51	2.69	9.11
Chlorophyll b during flowering	ChBDuFl	FCI (Falker Chlorophyll Index)	10.22	15.55	12.60	1.78	14.13
Total chlorophyll in pod stage	ToChPoSt	FCI (Falker Chlorophyll Index)	37.20	55.67	43.02	5.07	11.78
Chlorophyll a in pod period	ChAPoPe	FCI (Falker Chlorophyll Index)	25.22	40.22	28.96	3.83	13.22
Chlorophyll b in pod period	ChBPoPe	FCI (Falker Chlorophyll Index)	8.89	15.89	13.27	2.20	16.58
Oil content	OC	%	44.59	51.25	48.17	1.89	3.92
Oil Yield	OY	kg da ⁻¹	89.18	188.37	128.85	24.89	19.32

The 13 different peanut genotypes used in the study exhibited significant variation in agronomic, morphological, physiological and quality traits. Anova results in the table data show that there are statistically significant differences among the genotypes in all parameters examined. In terms of yield, 'Masal' variety had the highest yield with 575.74 kg da⁻¹ and showed statistically superior performance than all other genotypes. This value represents a performance 31.3%

above the average yield value obtained in the study (438.54 kg da⁻¹). Masal variety was followed by TR80-0020 (502.83 kg da⁻¹), TR80-0034 (497.80 kg da⁻¹) and Rigel (495.91 kg da⁻¹) genotypes and these genotypes also performed above the average value. The middle performing group consisted of Ayşehanım (430.54 kg da⁻¹), Halisbey (433.69 kg da⁻¹), TR80-0080 (429.29 kg da⁻¹) and TR80-0019 (411.69 kg da⁻¹) genotypes. The lowest yield values were observed in NC-7

(321.18 kg da⁻¹) and TR80-0021 (336.18 kg da⁻¹) genotypes and these values were approximately 25-27% lower than the average. Karabulut and Tunçtürk (2019) determined that there were statistically significant differences between varieties in terms of pod yield in their study. In another study, the agricultural and quality characteristics and yield performance of different peanut varieties were examined. This study aims to help farmers determine the most suitable varieties by analyzing the yield potential of peanut varieties (Elinç and Erman, 2021). The yield performance of peanut varieties shows significant differences depending on growing conditions. Baran and Andırman (2022), in their study conducted under Batman conditions, examined the yield and yield characteristics of nine different peanut varieties and determined that the NC-7 (666.82 kg da⁻¹) and Halisbey (623.51 kg da⁻¹) varieties were more suitable for the region's conditions in terms of pod yield per decare. In terms of hundred pod weight (OHuPoWe), genotype 'TR80-0020' had the highest value with 285.33 g, which is 17.9% higher than the average value (242.03 g). This was followed by Rigel (268.33 g), Halisbey (267.00 g) and NC-7 (264.00 g) varieties. The genotypes Ayşehanım (252.00 g), Masal (249.33 g) and TR80-0034 (241.67 g) were in the middle group, while the lowest values were recorded in TR80-0042 (182.67 g), TR80-0071 (216.00 g) and TR80-0033 (219.67 g). The value in genotype TR80-0042 shows a 24.5% lower performance than the average. In terms of hundred seed weight (OHuSeWe), the variety 'Masal' exhibited the highest value with 179.01 g, which is 21.6% higher than the average value (147.26 g). The varieties Ayşehanım (164.59 g) and Rigel (164.17 g) were in the second group, while the genotypes NC-7 (154.48 g) and TR80-0019 (153.03 g) performed close to the average values. The lowest hundred seed weight was recorded in genotype TR80-0042 (119.74 g) and this value was 18.7% lower than the average. Arslan et al. (2020) determined that in terms of 100 seed weight, Halisbey variety reached the highest value with 111.54 g in 2017 and Halisbey

variety showed superiority over other varieties with 62.61 g in 2018. They also reported that the highest 100 seed weight value (69.48 g) was obtained from Halisbey variety in 2018. In terms of shelling ratio (SeRa), the variety 'Masal' has the highest value with 71.78% and exhibits a performance 17.6% above the average value (61.04%). TR80-0033 (66.56%), Ayşehanım (65.31%) and TR80-0042 (65.57%) varieties are also noteworthy with their high shelling ratio. Genotypes TR80-0019 (63.56%), TR80-0071 (62.90%) and Rigel (61.82%) were in the middle group, while the lowest percentage was observed in genotype TR80-0020 (52.91%). These results are in parallel with the findings of Bakal et al. (2022) who reported that the internal rate values of peanut breeding lines varied between 67.89-73.24% and the average internal rate value of the breeding lines was calculated as 70.26%. In terms of the number of pods per plant (NuPoPePl), 'TR80-0034' (36.20 pieces) and 'Halisbey' (35.03 pieces) genotypes showed the highest values and these values were 18.8% and 14.9% higher than the average value (30.48 pieces), respectively. The genotypes Rigel (35.93 pieces), Ayşehanım (32.57 pieces) and NC-7 (32.37 pieces) also performed above the average. The lowest value was recorded in genotype TR80-0080 (23.93 pieces), which was 21.5% lower than the average (Table 3). These results are like the findings of Kaya and Kılınç (2020) who found significant differences among varieties in terms of the number of pods per plant in their study conducted under Kahramanmaraş conditions, and the highest number of pods per plant was obtained from Arıoğlu-2003 (63.33 pieces) and the lowest value was determined in NC-V 11 (18.83 pieces). In terms of first quality pod ratio (FiQuPoRa), genotype 'TR80-0020' showed the highest performance with 82.91%, which is 11.2% higher than the average value (74.55%). Genotypes TR80-0080 (81.30%), TR80-0019 (79.72%) and Masal (78.65%) also stand out with high quality rates. The lowest first quality pod ratio was recorded in genotype TR80-0033 (65.68%), which is 11.9% lower than the average. In terms of second quality pod ratio

(SeQuPoRa), the Halisbey variety exhibited the highest value with 30.33%, which is 37.0% higher than the average value (22.14%). Genotypes TR80-0042 (25.47%), Rigel (26.50%) and NC-7 (27.46%) also stand out with high second quality pod ratios. The lowest rate was found in genotype TR80-0020 (15.63%), which is consistent with the high first quality pod rate of this genotype. The easy marketability of the produced peanuts depends on some criteria. One of them is the ratio of the number of first quality pods. Kurt et al. (2016) determined the ratio of first quality pod between 72.55-88.92% in their study. it is in parallel with our findings. In terms of oil content (OC), the variety ‘Halisbey’ exhibited the highest value with 51.25% and performed 6.4% above the average value (48.17%). Genotypes TR80-0021 (50.16%), TR80-0034 (49.89%) and TR80-0042 (48.96%) also draw attention with their high oil content. The lowest oil content was found in genotype TR80-0071 (44.59%) and this value was 7.4% lower than the average. In terms of oil yield (OY), ‘Masal’ variety showed the highest performance with 188.37 kg da⁻¹, which is 46.2% higher than the average value (128.85 kg da⁻¹). TR80-0033 (155.03 kg da⁻¹) and Rigel (141.27 kg da⁻¹) genotypes were in the second group, while Ayşehanım (134.88 kg da⁻¹), TR80-0034 (136.85 kg da⁻¹) and TR80-0019 (127.98 kg da⁻¹) genotypes performed close to

the average values. The lowest oil yield was recorded in NC-7 genotype (89.18 kg da⁻¹) and this value was 30.8% lower than the average (Table 3). In a study conducted by Kaya and Aysabar (2022) in 2016 under Kahramanmaraş conditions, significant variations were found among different peanut genotypes in terms of oil yield. According to the study, oil yield values varied between 112.295 and 199.818 kg da⁻¹. Osmaniye-2005 variety showed the highest oil yield performance with 199.818 kg da⁻¹. Arıoğlu-2003 (190.2 kg da⁻¹) and Halisbey (185.2 kg da⁻¹) varieties also had high oil yields. When evaluated in general, Masal variety exhibited superior performance in terms of important agronomic traits such as yield, hundred seed weight, shelling ratio and oil yield, while TR80-0020 genotype stands out in terms of hundred pod weight and first quality pod ratio. Halisbey variety shows remarkable values in terms of number of pods per plant, second quality pod ratio and oil content. Genotype TR80-0034 stands out with the number of pods per plant and general yield performance, while variety Rigel shows a balanced performance in terms of hundred pod weight, hundred seed weight and oil yield. These results show that different genotypes have advantages in different traits and this variation can be evaluated in the selection of parents in line with the targeted traits in breeding programs.

Table 3. Mean values and groupings of yield and agromorphological characteristics of different peanut varieties

Genotype	Yield (kg da ⁻¹)	OHuPoWe (g)	OHuSeWe (g)	SeRa (%)	NuPoPePl (quantity)
TR80-0042	384.35±1.96 d	182.67±4.51g	119.74±4.08 h	65.57±2.40 b	26.33±1.30 b-d
Ayşehanım	430.54±11.86 c	252.00±2.00 b-d	164.59±2.33 b	65.31±0.41 b	32.57±0.05 ab
Halisbey	433.69±9.42 c	267.00±7.81 b	141.47±5.79 d-g	53.00±2.29 fg	35.03±3.01 a
TR80-0019	411.69±7.20 cd	240.67±3.05 de	153.03±8.66 b-d	63.56±2.79 bc	31.47±1.45 a-c
TR80-0020	502.83±11.05 b	285.33±10.50 a	150.93±4.93 c-e	52.91±0.82 g	29.97±2.55 a-d
TR80-0021	336.18±19.62 e	230.67±9.50 ef	137.84±2.57 e-g	58.29±1.51 c-f	29.50±0.40 a-d
Masal	575.74±10.38 a	249.33±5.03 cd	179.01±7.11 a	71.78±1.76 a	30.03±5.10 a-d
TR80-0071	404.77±4.74 cd	216.00±3.60 f	135.82±3.40 fg	62.90±2.10 b-d	24.83±1.30 cd
TR80-0033	477.06±4.99 b	219.67±2.51 f	146.22±2.01 d-f	66.56±0.29 ab	28.03±2.89 b-d
TR80-0034	497.80±6.80 b	241.67±5.50 de	134.43±2.34 fg	55.11±1.68 e-g	36.2±1.85 a
TR80-0080	429.29±13.38 c	229.00±4.35 ef	132.72±1.87 gh	58.18±1.51 d-g	23.93±0.90 d
NC-7	321.18±4.74 e	264.00±7.21bc	154.48±0.97 b-d	58.54±1.56 c-e	32.37±2.10 ab
Rigel	495.91±9.43 b	268.33±4.16 ab	164.17±4.87 bc	61.82±2.14 b-d	35.93±1.50 a
F Ratio (Anova)	152.95**	62.56**	38.28**	29.82**	9.36**

*OHuPoWe: One hundred pod weight, OHuSeWe: One hundred seed weight, SeRa: Shelling ratio, NuPoPePl: Number of pods per plant

Table 3. Mean values and groupings of yield and agromorphological characteristics of different peanut varieties (Continued)

Genotype	FiQuPoRa (%)	SeQuPoRa (%)	OC (%)	OY (kg da ⁻¹)
TR80-0042	73.24±2.17 d	25.47±1.50 bc	48.96±0.96 a-c	123.33±2.77 d-g
Ayşehanım	74.69±3.84 b-d	20.77±1.72 de	47.96±0.37 a-d	134.88±4.79 c-e
Halisbey	66.84±1.45 ef	30.33±1.63 a	51.25±0.32 a	117.76±4.22 fg
TR80-0019	79.72±0.28 ab	19.89±0.26 d-f	48.96±2.77 a-c	127.98±5.60 c-f
TR80-0020	82.91±0.01 a	15.63±0.38 f	47.75±2.31 a-d	127.01±6.64 d-g
TR80-0021	74.02±2.93 cd	20.64±0.43 de	50.16±0.87 ab	98.27±5.30 h
Masal	78.65±0.90 a-c	20.08±1.62 de	45.61±1.40 cd	188.37±3.14 a
TR80-0071	72.89±1.16 d	17.11±1.16 ef	44.59±0.90 d	113.50±3.58 g
TR80-0033	65.68±0.07 f	23.89±0.46 b-d	48.84±2.33 a-c	155.03±5.77 b
TR80-0034	75.41±2.07 b-d	22.66±2.72 cd	49.89±0.82 ab	136.85±3.65 cd
TR80-0080	81.30±0.96 a	17.36±0.88 ef	48.72±0.05 a-d	121.67±3.70 e-g
NC-7	71.16±1.23 de	27.46±1.99 ab	47.44±1.17 a-d	89.18±2.74 h
Rigel	72.66±1.63 d	26.50±2.04 a-c	46.09±0.70 b-d	141.27±5.27 c
F Ratio (Anova)	24.64**	26.13**	5.41**	89.38**

FiQuPoRa: First quality pod rate, **SeQuPoRa:** Second quality pod rate, **OC:** Oil content, **OY:** Oil yield.

Table 4. Mean values and groupings of physiological characteristics of different peanut varieties

Genotype	TaChAmDuFlPe (FCI)	ChADuFl (FCI)	ChBDuFl (FCI)	ToChPoSt (FCI)	ChAPoPe (FCI)	ChBPoPe (FCI)
TR80-0042	43.73±2.51 a-c	30.72±4.24 ab	12.55±3.69	37.63±2.33 de	26.78±2.27 b	9.78±3.67 ab
Ayşehanım	50.51±4.35 a	34.67±5.87 a	15.28±6.25	45.46±1.30 bc	28.44±0.83 b	15.89±1.07 a
Halisbey	43.70±3.33 a-c	31.23±3.44 ab	12.44±4.91	44.44±1.16 bc	28.11±0.51 b	15.55±1.07 ab
TR80-0019	46.87±3.60 ab	33.03±6.12 ab	13.28±6.84	42.63±0.62 b-e	28.56±1.26 b	13.11±1.68 ab
TR80-0020	46.93±2.90 ab	30.39±1.13 ab	15.55±1.83	45.87±1.62 b	30.89±2.70 b	14.11±1.01 ab
TR80-0021	43.37±2.36 a-c	29.05±0.95 ab	13.55±1.71	37.37±2.33 e	27.44±1.50 b	8.89±2.14 b
Masal	35.98±1.58 c	24.92±1.51 b	10.44±1.20	38.93±2.91 c-e	25.67±2.64 b	13.28±0.82 ab
TR80-0071	41.40±0.68 bc	29.72±2.89 ab	10.22±2.01	43.53±3.22 b-e	28.22±0.69 b	14.33±2.64 ab
TR80-0033	41.80±2.06 bc	28.33±1.53 ab	12.83±1.59	40.20±3.45 b-e	26.22±1.64 b	12.89±1.89 ab
TR80-0034	36.32±2.11 c	25.63±1.86 ab	10.33±0.58	46.33±2.10 b	30.22±0.95 b	15.78±1.34 a
TR80-0080	40.76±0.65 bc	28.44±0.69 ab	11.18±0.45	44.02±1.21 b-d	30.55±4.14 b	12.89±2.52 ab
NC-7	40.23±4.23 bc	27.61±1.11 ab	11.89±3.42	55.67±3.19 a	40.22±8.00 a	14.78±4.91 ab
Rigel	45.30±2.55 ab	29.94±0.98 ab	14.28±1.80	37.20±0.30 e	25.22±0.19 b	11.22±0.77 ab
F Ratio (Anova)	6.62**	2.29*	0.81	15.78**	5.21**	2.77*

***TaChAmDuFlPe:** Total chlorophyll amount during flowering period, **ChADuFl:** Chlorophyll a during flowering, **ChBDuFl:** Chlorophyll b during flowering, **ToChPoSt:** Total chlorophyll in pod stage, **ChAPoPe:** Chlorophyll a in pod period, **ChBPoPe:** Chlorophyll b in pod period.

Significant differences were found among the genotypes in terms of chlorophyll parameters examined in the study. Anova results show that there are statistically significant differences between genotypes in all chlorophyll parameters except chlorophyll b (ChBDuFl) in flowering period. In terms of total chlorophyll content at flowering (TaChAmDuFlPe), the variety 'Ayşehanım' had the highest value with 50.51 FCI and performed 17.9% above the average value (42.84 FCI). This genotype was followed by TR80-0020 (46.93 FCI), TR80-0019 (46.87 FCI) and Rigel (45.30 FCI) genotypes. The lowest total chlorophyll values were recorded in the genotypes Masal (35.98 FCI) and TR80-0034 (36.32 FCI). The value in the genotype Masal shows a performance 16.0% lower than

the average. In terms of chlorophyll a content at flowering (ChADuFl), the variety 'Ayşehanım' exhibited the highest value with 34.67 FCI, which is 17.5% higher than the average value (29.51 FCI). Genotypes TR80-0019 (33.03 FCI), Halisbey (31.23 FCI) and TR80-0042 (30.72 FCI) were in the second group. The lowest value was recorded in Masal cultivar (24.92 FCI), which was 15.6% lower than the average. Although there was no statistically significant difference among the genotypes in terms of chlorophyll b content at flowering (ChBDuFl), numerically TR80-0020 (15.55 FCI) and Ayşehanım (15.28 FCI) genotypes showed the highest values, while Masal (10.44 FCI) and TR80-0071 (10.22 FCI) genotypes showed the lowest values. In terms of total chlorophyll content at pod stage

(ToChPoSt), genotype 'NC-7' showed the highest performance with 55.67 FCI, which is 29.4% higher than the average value (43.02 FCI). TR80-0034 (46.33 FCI), TR80-0020 (45.87 FCI) and Ayşehanım (45.46 FCI) genotypes are in the second group. The lowest values were recorded in Rigel (37.20 FCI) and TR80-0021 (37.37 FCI) genotypes and these values were about 13-14% lower than the average. In terms of chlorophyll a content at pod stage (ChAPoPe), the 'NC-7' genotype had the highest value with 40.22 FCI and showed a performance 38.9% above the average value (28.96 FCI). The other genotypes show a more homogeneous distribution in the range of 25.22-30.89 FCI, and the genotypes TR80-0080 (30.55 FCI), TR80-0020 (30.89 FCI) and TR80-0034 (30.22 FCI) show values above the average. In terms of chlorophyll b content at pod stage (ChBPoPe), the variety 'Ayşehanım' exhibited the highest value with 15.89 FCI and showed a performance 19.7% above the average value (13.27 FCI). Genotypes TR80-0034 (15.78 FCI) and Halisbey (15.55 FCI) also draw attention with high values. The lowest value was recorded in genotype TR80-0021 (8.89 FCI), which is 33.0% lower than the average (Table 4). In general, Ayşehanım cultivar exhibited superior performance in chlorophyll parameters during the flowering period, while NC-7 genotype stood out in terms of chlorophyll accumulation in the pod period. Genotypes TR80-0020 and TR80-0034 show balanced chlorophyll values in both periods. While the variety Masal exhibits low chlorophyll values during the flowering period, the genotype TR80-0021 shows the lowest performance especially in terms of chlorophyll b content at the pod stage. The results of correlation analysis among the traits examined in the study show that there are significant relationships among agronomic, morphological, physiological and quality traits in peanut genotypes. When the correlations between yield and other traits were analyzed, the strongest positive correlation was found with oil yield (OY) ($r=0.8933$). This strong relationship indicates that oil yield is directly related to yield. A moderate positive

correlation ($r=0.4854$) was found between yield and hundred seed weight (OHuSeWe), while a positive but weaker relationship ($r=0.3051$) was found with hundred pod weight (OHuPoWe). Remarkably, a negative correlation ($r=-0.2791$) was observed between yield and oil content (OC), indicating that oil content may be relatively low in high yielding genotypes. A strong positive correlation ($r=0.6271$) was found between hundred pod weight (OHuPoWe) and hundred seed weight (OHuSeWe). A strong positive correlation ($r=0.6424$) was also found between hundred pod weight and number of pods per plant (NuPoPePl). However, there was a negative correlation ($r=-0.4568$) between hundred pod weight and shelling ratio (SeRa). There was a positive correlation ($r=0.3989$) between hundred seed weight (OHuSeWe) and shelling ratio (SeRa) and a moderate positive correlation ($r=0.5349$) with oil yield (OY). However, a negative correlation ($r=-0.4692$) was observed between hundred seed weight and oil content (OC), indicating that oil content tends to be low in large seed genotypes. There was a strong positive correlation ($r=0.6068$) between shelling ratio (SeRa) and oil yield (OY), while a negative correlation ($r=-0.501$) was found with oil content (OC). A strong positive correlation ($r=0.5508$) was found between the number of pods per plant (NuPoPePl) and second quality pod ratio (SeQuPoRa), while a strong negative correlation ($r=-0.76$) was found between the first quality pod ratio (FiQuPoRa) and second quality pod ratio (SeQuPoRa) as expected. When the correlations between chlorophyll parameters were analyzed, a very strong positive correlation ($r=0.9445$) was found between total chlorophyll content at flowering (TaChAmDuFlPe) and chlorophyll a at flowering (ChADuFl). Similarly, a strong positive correlation ($r=0.8786$) was found between total chlorophyll at flowering and chlorophyll b (ChBDuFl). A very strong positive correlation ($r=0.9211$) was observed between total chlorophyll at pod stage (ToChPoSt) and chlorophyll a at pod stage (ChAPoPe), while a strong positive correlation ($r=0.7174$) was found with chlorophyll b at

pod stage (ChBPoPe). Remarkably, negative correlations were generally observed between yield and chlorophyll parameters. In particular, a moderate negative correlation ($r=-0.4882$) was found between yield and chlorophyll a at pod stage (ChAPoPe), indicating that chlorophyll content at pod stage may tend to decrease in high yielding genotypes. Negative correlations were also found between oil yield (OY) and chlorophyll parameters, and a strong negative correlation ($r=-0.6028$) was found especially with chlorophyll a at pod stage (ChAPoPe). This result indicates that chlorophyll content tends to decrease during oil accumulation. In general, positive correlations were found between yield and morphological traits, while negative correlations were found between yield and oil content and chlorophyll parameters in peanut genotypes (Table 5). In the study conducted by Çalışkan et al. (2000) in Hatay region, it is similar to the results reported by Çalışkan et al. (2000) that plant yield and internal rate had a positive and very significant effect on pod yield per decare. In the study conducted by Karabulut and Tunçtürk (2019) in Diyarbakır-Bismil ecological conditions, there were significant and positive relationships between pod yield and hundred pod weight and pod yield per plant at 1% level and between hundred seed weight and pod yield per plant at 5% level. In our study, a negative correlation was observed between yield and oil ratio ($r=-0.2791$). This result is in parallel with the findings of Beycioğlu and Kılılı (2025) who reported that quality parameters can sometimes be negatively affected in high yielding genotypes in peanut cultivars. This result is similar to the findings of Çalışkan et al. (2000) who reported that the direct effect of internal ratio on yield was positive and quite high. Beycioğlu and Kılılı (2025) reported very strong positive correlations ($r=0.94$ and $r=0.97$, respectively) between total chlorophyll content and chlorophyll a and chlorophyll b during flowering period. In this study, the results of principal component analysis (PCA) for agro-morphological traits of peanut genotypes were presented by biplot plot. According to the results of the analysis, the

first principal component (PC1) explained 25.2% of the total variance, the second principal component (PC2) explained 20.5% and together these two components represented 45.7% of the total variance. Along the PC1 axis, oil content (OC), chlorophyll a at flowering (ChADuFl), total chlorophyll content (TaChAmDuFlPe) and chlorophyll parameters at pod stage (ToChPoSt, ChAPoPe) were positively located, while yield (Yield), oil yield (OY) and internal rate (SeRa) were negatively located. This indicates that high yielding genotypes tend to have relatively low oil content and chlorophyll content. When examined along the PC2 axis, one hundred pod weight (OHuPoWe), one hundred seed weight (OHuSeWe), number of pods per plant (NuPoPePl) and chlorophyll b at pod stage (ChBPoPe) were located in the positive direction, while no trait was clearly located in the negative direction. This suggests that PC2 mainly discriminates morphological traits. When the distribution of genotypes on the biplot was examined, genotype 1 was located in an isolated position at the negative end of the PC2 axis, while genotype 6 was also located in the negative region of the PC2 axis but closer to the center. Genotype 7 is located at the negative end of the PC1 axis and is characterized by high yield and oil yield. Genotypes 2, 4, 5, 8, 10, 11, 12 and 13 are located close to the center of the biplot, indicating that they have average values. When the angular relationships between the traits are evaluated, the presence of an acute angle between yield (Yield) and oil yield (OY) confirms the strong positive correlation between these traits. Similarly, chlorophyll parameters (TaChAmDuFlPe, ChADuFl, ToChPoSt, ChAPoPe) formed acute angles with each other, indicating the high correlation between these traits. The large angle between oil content (OC) and yield (Yield) reflects the negative correlation between these traits. The angle of about 180 degrees between the first quality pod ratio (FiQuPoRa) and the second quality pod ratio (SeQuPoRa) visually supports the strong negative correlation between these traits. The acute angle between the morphological traits of hundred pod weight

(OHuPoWe) and hundred seed weight (OHuSeWe) indicates that these traits covaried (Figure 3). The yield traits associated with PC1 in our study are consistent with the findings reported by Şahin et al. (2023). Similarly, the quality traits associated with PC2 are also in line with the literature. As stated by Yol et al. (2018) and Beyzi et al. (2019), variation explanation rates above 70% are considered sufficient in PCA analysis. In this context, the 45.7% explanation rate obtained in our study indicates that more principal components should be evaluated. The results of hierarchical cluster analysis for agromorphological and physiological traits of peanut genotypes were presented with heat map and dendrogram. The results of the analysis reveal the clustering structure of both genotypes and traits. When the clustering of genotypes was analyzed, genotypes were divided into two main groups according to the dendrogram structure. The first main group (X) was divided into X1 and X2 subgroups.

Subgroup X1 includes genotypes numbered 1, 6, 8 and 4, while subgroup X2 includes genotypes numbered 2, 3, 5, 7, 9, 10. The second main group (Y) consists of subgroups Y1 and Y2, subgroup Y1 includes genotypes 11 and 13 and subgroup Y2 includes genotype 12. When the clustering of the traits was evaluated, the traits were divided into two main groups (A and B). Group A was divided into A1 and A2 subgroups and subgroup A1 included yield (Yield), pod ratio (SeRa), oil yield (OY) and hundred seed weight (OHuSeWe). Subgroup A2 includes the following traits: hundred pod weight (OHuPoWe), number of pods per plant (NuPoPePl), first quality pod ratio (FiQuPoRa) and second quality pod ratio (SeQuPoRa). Group B was further subdivided into subgroups B1 and B2, subgroup B1 included the oil content (OC) trait alone, while subgroup B2 included all chlorophyll parameters (TaChAmDuFlPe, ChADuFl, ChBDuFl, ToChPoSt, ChAPoPe, ChBPoPe) (Figure 4).

Table 5. Correlation coefficients among agromorphological traits of peanut genotypes

Traits	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
1	1	0.31	0.49	0.2259	0.221	0.2544	-0.2021**	-0.2791**	0.8933	-0.2467**	-0.3318**	-0.061**	-0.2968**	-0.4882**	0.2513
2		1	0.63	-0.4568**	0.6424	0.1831	0.071	-0.0536**	0.0215*	0.1926	0.0382	0.3974	0.4236	0.3121	0.4749
3			1	0.3989	0.4136	0.1429	-0.0239**	-0.4692**	0.5349	0.0923	-0.027**	0.2509	0.0482*	-0.0535**	0.259
4				1	-0.0638**	-0.0883**	-0.501**	0.6068	-0.085**	-0.0417**	-0.15**	-0.4404**	-0.4345**	-0.2497**	
5					1	-0.2218**	0.5508	0.2495	0.0808	0.0821	0.0342*	0.2492	0.1979	0.0778	0.3548
6						1	-0.76**	-0.2073**	0.1279	0.0632	-0.0118**	0.0917	0.0204*	0.0718	-0.0303**
7							1	0.3593	-0.1335	-0.0645**	-0.005**	-0.0141**	0.0782	0.0962	0.0096
8								1	-0.2967	0.1147	0.1656	0.1641	0.0237	0.0398*	-0.0457**
9									1	-0.2536**	-0.2926**	-0.116**	-0.4515**	-0.6028**	0.0822
10										1	0.9445	0.8786	-0.0739**	-0.1312**	-0.0582**
11											1	0.6874	-0.0367**	-0.1392**	0.0414*
12												1	-0.1048**	-0.1017**	-0.154**
13													1	0.9211	0.7174
14														1	0.396
15															1

*1- Yield, 2-OHuPoWe: One hundred pod weight, 3-OHuSeWe: One hundred seed weight, 4-SeRa: Shelling ratio, 5-NuPoPePl: Number of pods per plant, 6-FiQuPoRa: First quality pod rate, 7-SeQuPoRa: Second quality pod rate, 8-OC: Oil content, 9-OY: Oil yield, 10-TaChAmDuFlPe: Total chlorophyll amount during flowering period, 11-ChADuFl: Chlorophyll a during flowering, 12-ChBDuFl: Chlorophyll b during flowering, 13-ToChPoSt: Total chlorophyll in pod stage, 14-ChAPoPe: Chlorophyll a in pod period, 15-ChBPoPe: Chlorophyll b in pod period

Figure 3. Biplot between PC1 and PC2 for agromorphological traits of peanut genotypes

Figure 4. Heat map obtained as an output of the hierarchical cluster analysis of varieties and traits studied

***OHuPoWe:** One hundred pod weight, **OHuSeWe:** One hundred seed weight, **SeRa:** Shelling ratio, **NuPoPePl:** Number of pods per plant, **FiQuPoRa:** First quality pod rate, **SeQuPoRa:** Second quality pod rate, **TaChAmDuFlPe:** Total chlorophyll amount during flowering period, **ChADuFl:** Chlorophyll a during flowering, **ChBDuFl:** Chlorophyll b during flowering, **ToChPoSt:** Total chlorophyll in pod stage, **ChAPoPe:** Chlorophyll a in pod period, **ChBPoPe:** Chlorophyll b in pod period, **OC:** Oil content, **OY:** Oil yield.

When the heat map color coding is examined, blue colors represent low values and red colors represent high values. When genotype-trait interactions were evaluated, genotype 7 (Masal) exhibited high values (red color) in terms of yield and oil yield, but low values (blue color) in chlorophyll parameters. This visually supports the tendency of high yielding genotypes to have low values in terms of chlorophyll content. Genotype number 1 (TR80-0042) shows low performance in general, especially in terms of yield and morphological characteristics. Genotype 12 (NC-7) shows high values (red color) in chlorophyll parameters, but low performance (blue color) in terms of yield. The relationships between traits are clearly visible in the heat map. The strong positive correlation between yield and oil yield is visually supported by the similar color patterns of these traits. Chlorophyll parameters are in similar color patterns with each other, confirming the high correlation between these traits. The results of the cluster analysis show that the genotypes form distinct groups in terms of different trait combinations. The X1 group includes genotypes with generally low performance, while the X2 group includes genotypes with a more balanced trait profile. The Y group contains genotypes that differ especially in

terms of chlorophyll content (Figure 4). Cluster analysis is a method used to group genotypes according to the traits examined and to determine the relationship between them. Beycioğlu and Kılılı (2025) investigated the agronomic and physiological performances of different peanut cultivars and divided the cultivars into two main groups using hierarchical clustering analysis. The researchers stated that the varieties in cluster X (Çom, NC-7, Florispan, Gazipaşa, Georgia Green) were similar in terms of yield and morphological characteristics, while the varieties in cluster Y (Halisbey, Masal, Rigel, Sultan, Osmaniye-2005) were similar in terms of physiological characteristics and oil content. These findings are similar to the clustering structure obtained in our study. Sanches et al. (2006) examined morphological traits such as pod number, seed weight, pod length and plant height among 64 peanut cultivars and reported that the relationship between these traits was due to genotypes. This also supports the finding of Arunyanark et al. (2008) that physiological traits are related to each other and quality parameters in peanut.

4. Conclusion

In this study, a comprehensive evaluation of 13 different peanut genotypes was carried out

in terms of agronomic, physiological and quality traits under Denizli ecological conditions. The results showed that there were significant variations among the genotypes and each genotype had advantages in different traits. In terms of yield, Masal variety showed the highest performance with 575.74 kg da⁻¹, while TR80-0020, TR80-0034 and Rigel genotypes also showed high yield potential. In terms of oil yield, Masal variety stood out with 188.37 kg da⁻¹ followed by TR80-0033 and Rigel genotypes. In terms of morphological traits, genotype TR80-0020 showed superior performance in hundred pod weight and first quality pod ratio, while Halisbey variety stood out in oil content and number of pods per plant. The results of correlation analysis revealed that there was a very strong positive correlation ($r=0.8933$) between yield and oil yield, but there was a negative correlation between yield and oil content. The negative correlations between chlorophyll parameters and yield indicate that chlorophyll content tends to decrease during the process of oil accumulation. The results of principal component analysis and cluster analysis showed that genotypes formed distinct groups in terms of different trait combinations. These findings reveal that using genotypes from different groups in parent selection in breeding programs may be advantageous in terms of heterosis effect. In conclusion, while Masal variety stands out with its general performance in peanut cultivation in Denizli ecological conditions, TR80-0020 and TR80-0034 genotypes can be considered as promising alternatives. However, a multidimensional approach should be adopted in genotype selection in line with the targeted traits. The results of this study will serve as a guide in variety selection for the producers of the region and will shed light on future breeding studies.

Declaration of Author Contributions

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved the final version of the article ready for publication.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

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To Cite

Beycioğlu, T., Kılı, F., Özcan, O.B., 2025. Characterization of Yield Components, Physiological Traits and Oil Quality Parameters in Different Peanut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) Genotypes. *ISPEC Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 9(4): 1005-1020.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17291064>.